

**Taxonomy structure of *Agapanthia (Epoptes) asphodeli* (Latreille, 1804)
(Coleoptera, Cerambycidae)**

M.A. Lazarev

Free Economic Society of Russia, Department of Scientifics Conferences and All-Russian Projects

Tverskaya str., 22a, Moscow 125009 Russia

e-mail: cerambycidae@bk.ru, humanityspace@gmail.com

Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, taxonomy, zoogeography, new status, new subspecies, new synonyms, name restored.

Abstract: The taxonomy of the species is revised; 8 subspecies are accepted: *Agapanthia (Epoptes) a. asphodeli* (Latreille, 1804) - type locality France, Bordeaux environs; *A. (E.) a. lopadusae* Rapuzzi & Sparacio, 2017, **stat. n.** - type locality Italy, Sicilian Channel, Lampedusa Island; *A. (E.) a. renatae* Steiner & Schmid, 2013, **stat. n.** - type locality Greece, Peloponnese, Arcadia, between Karitena and Kastro; *A. (E.) a. cretica* Bernhauer, 1978, **stat. n.** - type locality Crete, Mount Ida, Anogia; *A. (E.) a. kastamonica ssp. n.* - type locality Turkey, Kastamonu province, Yaralıgöz Dağı; *A. (E.) a. nicosiensis* Pic, 1927 is restored to its original rank - type locality Cyprus; *A. (E.) a. zappii* Sama, 1987, **stat. n.** - type locality Algeria (Batna), Telmet canyon (Aures Mountains), 1700 m; *A. (E.) a. fadli* Sama & Rapuzzi, 2006, **stat. n.** - type locality "14 km east of Burg al 'Arab (west of Alexandria), 30°58'N 29°40'E". One subspecies is described as new and the species rank of five names is downgraded to subspecies level. Two new synonyms are proposed: *A. (E.) renatae* Steiner & Schmid, 2013 = *A. (E.) asphodeli balcanica* Sláma, 2019, **syn. n.**; *A. (E.) cretica* Bernhauer, 1978 = *A. (E.) probsti* Holzschuh, 1984, **syn. n.** The holotype of *A. reyi* Mulsant & Godart, 1870 is depicted for the first time, so the synonymy by Sama (1979) *A. (E.) asphodeli* = *A. (E.) reyi* Mulsant & Godart, 1870 is proved.

Introduction

Agapanthia asphodeli (Latreille, 1804) is a rare poorly investigated species. Many local populations were described as separate species; sometimes (Lucas, 1848; Pic, 1927) *A. asphodeli* was mixed with *A. boeberi* (Fischer von Waldheim, 1806). Spanish populations of *A. asphodeli* were long time accepted as *A. reyi* Mulsant & Godart, 1870 after wrong identification of the holotype of the later. The area of the species was treated by many authors for the regions, where no specimens were available from now (Plavilstshikov, 1948 - Arax valley; 1965 - steppe area, Crimea; 1968

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- steppe area of USSR eastwards Urals and Transcaucasia; Ogloblin, 1948 - south of forest-steppe and steppe area of European USSR; Danilevsky & Miroschnikov, 1985 - European USSR, Transcaucasia; Prisnyj & Vorobieva, 2005 - Belgorod. Only one male (from Teberda) is available now from Russia.

So, the actual adequate information is necessary to be published.

I accept the species with 8 subspecies:

1. *A. (E.) a. asphodeli* (Latreille, 1804)
Type locality. France, Bordeaux environs.
2. *A. (E.) a. lopadusae* Rapuzzi & Sparacio, 2017, **stat. n.**
Type locality. Italy, Sicilian Channel, Lampedusa Island.
3. *A. (E.) a. renatae* Steiner & Schmid, 2013, **stat. n.**
Type locality. Greece, Peloponnese, Arcadia, between Karitena and Kastro.
4. *A. (E.) a. cretica* Bernhauer, 1978, **stat. n.**
Type locality. Crete, Mount Ida, Anogia.
5. *A. (E.) a. kastamonica* **ssp. n.**
Type locality. Turkey, Kastamonu province, Yaralığöz Dağı.
6. *A. (E.) a. nicosiensis* Pic, 1927, **stat. rest.**
Type locality. Cyprus.
7. *A. (E.) a. zappii* Sama, 1987, **stat. n.**
Type locality. Algeria (Batna), Telmet canyon (Aures Mountains), 1700 m.
8. *A. (E.) a. fadli* Sama & Rapuzzi, 2006, **stat. n.**
Type locality. “14 km east of Burg al ‘Arab (west of Alexandria), 30°58’N 29°40’E”.

Material and method

Material was collected manually. Specimens used in morphological studies were killed by ethyl acetate. All photographs were taken with Canon PowerShot G10 digital camera equipped with Cannon Zoom lens 5X IS 6.1-30.5 mm 1:2.8-4.5 and microscope AmScope SM745NTP. The illustrations were edited with Adobe Photoshop 7.0 and Helicon Focus 3.20.

Acronyms of collections:

MD - collection of M.L. Danilevsky (Moscow)

ML - collection of M.A. Lazarev (Moscow)

SM - collection of S.V. Murzin (Moscow)

MNHN - collection of Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle (Paris)

ZMM - collection of Zoological Museum of Moscow University

Results

Agapanthia (Epopetes) asphodeli (Latreille, 1804)

Lamia asphodeli Latreille, 1804:282 - “environs de Bordeaux”.

Saperda asphodelis, Westwood, 1839: 365.

Agapanthia cynarae var. *delagrangei* Pic, 1894: 75 - “Akbès”.

Agapanthia delagrangei, Plavilstshikov, 1932: 199, part. (= *A. verecunda* Chevrolat, 1882).

Agapanthia asphodeli m. *mimica*, Breuning, 1961: 184.

Agapanthia asphodeli, Plavilstshikov, 1932: 194 - south of USSR, Caucasus; 1965: 416 - steppe area, Crimea, Caucasus; Ogloblin, 1948: 469 - south of forest-steppe and steppe area of European USSR; Villiers, 1978: 435 - “Europe méridionale et centrale, Caucase, Asie Mineure, Afrique du Nord”; Sama, 1979: 508, 511; 1992: 399 (= *reysi* Mulsant & Godart, 1870); 2003: 93 - Europe, North Africa, Asia Minor, Caucasus, Transcaucasia; Baragaño Galan et al., 1981: 161; Kasatkin & Arzanov, 1997: 67 - Anapa; Jeniš, 2001: 260; Prisnyj & Vorobieva, 2005: 40 - Belgorod.

Agapanthia (s. str.) *asphodeli*, Plavilstshikov, 1948: 167 - Arax valley; Caucasus; 1968: 143 - steppe area of USSR eastwards Urals, Caucasus and Transcaucasia; Danilevsky & Miroshnikov, 1985: 390 - European USSR, Caucasus, Transcaucasia.

Agapanthia (Agapanthiella) asphodeli, Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2004: 12; Özdikmen 2007: 347 - Europe (Portugal, Spain, France, Corsica, Italy, Sicily, Sardinia, Malta, Croatia, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Macedonia, Albania, Greece, Romania, Switzerland, ?Sweden, Ukraine, Crimea, ? Moldavia, European Russia), Kazakhstan, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Central Asia, Turkey, ?Syria, ?Palestine, ?North Africa, (Turkey: Adana-Ankara-Antalya-Aydin-Bilecik- Çanakkale-Hatay-Isparta-Izmir-Yozgat Provinces); 2008a: 77 - Turkey; 2008b: 394 - Turkey.

Agapanthia (Epopetes) asphodeli, Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 215 - Azerbaijan, Albania, Armenia, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, France, Georgia, Greece, Italy, Malta, Macedonia, Moldavia, Portugal, Spain, Russia: South European Territory, Slovenia, Ukraine, Kazakhstan, Turkey; Özdikmen, 2013: 16 - “Turkey: (W half of Anatolia)”; Rapuzzi & Sparacio, 2017: 957 - “from Spain and Portugal to Southern Russia, West Kazakhstan, Balcan Peninsula and Asia Minor (locus typicus: Bordeaux, France)”; Kasatkin, 2020: 242, 243; Danilevsky, 2023: 592.

Agapanthia (Epopetes) asphodeli asphodeli Danilevsky, 2020: 301 - E: Albania, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, France, Greece, Italy, Malta, Macedonia, ?Moldavia, Portugal, Romania, Spain, ?Russia: South European Territory, Slovenia, ?Ukraine, N: Morocco ?A: Azerbaijan, Armenia,

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Georgia, Kazakhstan, Turkey; Özdikmen, 2021: 1351 E: Albania, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, France, Greece, Italy, Malta, Macedonia, ?Moldavia, Portugal, Romania, Spain, ?Russia: South European Territory, Slovenia, ?Ukraine, N: Morocco, ?A: Azerbaijan, Armenia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Turkey.

Type locality. France, Bordeaux environs.

Description. Relatively big species with moderately narrow body, covered with more or less dense yellow pubescence; eyes small, with lower lobes shorter than length of genae or rather big, about two times longer, than genae; antennae usually thin, very long, in males about two times longer than body, surpassing elytral apex by 6th joint; in females - by 8th joint; most of basal parts of 3rd - 12th reddish or dark-brown; apical parts black; 3rd joint always without setae tufts, sometimes with a poor concentration of several long setae; prothorax transverse, angulate widened at middle; pronotum with dense and wide central yellow setae line, without recumbent pubescence along its sides, with very numerous long erect setae; scutellum semicircular with very dense recumbent yellow pubescence; elytra about 2.8-3.0 times longer than basal width, with moderately sharpened apices; poorly spotted elytral pubescence rather sparse, so elytral shine can be distinct; erect setae are distributed from elytral base to the apex; elytral punctation very dense with interspaces less than each dot; grey humeral line can be distinct in certain subspecies; 3rd joint of anterior tarsi elongated; 1st and 2nd joints together of posterior legs longer than 3rd; ventral body side with very dense yellow pubescence; last abdominal tergites in males truncated, sternites - slightly emarginates; last abdominal tergites and sternites in females rounded; body length in males: 10.5-17.2 mm, body length in females: 13.8-23.0 mm.

Distribution. The species is distributed in Europe from Portugal along south Europe to Slovakia, Hungary, Greece, Bulgaria, and Turkey; it is also known from Ukraine and Moldavia, widely distributed in Anatolia and North Africa

(Egypt, Morocco, Lybia, Algeria, Tunisia). The species was also recorded from Syria. All numerous records from Russia, Transcaucasia and Kazakhstan must be proved, as a single old male only is available from North Caucasus (Teberda), and no specimens are available from Transcaucasia and Kazakhstan. The records from Iran (Sakenin, 2011: 6 - “Ardabil province: Meshkinshahr”) are doubtful.

Biology. Larvae are connected with stems of *Asphodelus*; *Thapsia* and *Ferula* were also recorded; all records of Carduaceae are very doubtful; imagoes are active from April to June.

Many *Agapanthia* species close to *A. asphodeli* (Latreille, 1804) were listed by Rapuzzi & Sparacio (2017), but most of them are in fact good subspecies of *A. asphodeli* (Latreille, 1804).

Agapanthia (Epoptes) asphodeli asphodeli (Latreille, 1804)

Figs 1-3, 7

Lamia asphodeli Latreille, 1804:282 - “environs de Bordeaux”.

Saperda spencii Gyllenhal, 1817: 187 - “Gallia meridionali”.

Agapanthia asphodeli, Mulsant 1839: 174 - “midi de la France”; 1862: 355 - “espèce méridionale”; Küster, 1846: 66 - “Im südlichen Frankreich”; Chernay, 1854: 252 - Kharkov; Gemminger & Harold, 1873: 3175 - “Gallia mer., Hungaria”; Perris, 1877: 340 - “Hyères”; Ganglbauer, 1884: 541, part. - “Süd-Europa, Kleinasien”; Seidlitz, 1891: 849 - “Im südl. Eur.”; Reitter, 1898: 130 - “Südeuropa, Kleinasien”; 1913: 66 - “in Böhmen”; Winkler, 1929: 1213 - Bohemia, Transsylvania, Mediterranea; Bonnamour, 1935: 107 - “Dans l'Isère: Vienne, la Grande-Chartreuse”; Schaefer 1947 - France: Banyuls -sur-Mer; Breuning, 1961: 184, part. - “Eur. centr. et mer., As. mer. occ.”; Carrière, 1996a: 64 - “Hérault”; 1996b: 562 - “Aude, Hérault”; 1996c: 110, 111 - “Les Baumes, Causse de Neffîès; La Redoute-plage; Bois Mégé, Vissous”; 2001: 404 - “Hérault”; 2003: 257, 258 - “Causse de Neffîès (Hérault)”; 2005: 468 - “Causse de Fauzan”; 2007: 551 - “Pic de Vissous, Grange de Couderc, Pech Haut, Roque-Nègre, Cabrières (Montagne des Batailles)”; Verdugo-Páez, 1999: 19 - “San Fernando”, “Puerto Real”, “Sierra Grazalema”, “Alcalá de los Gazules”; Sudre et al., 1999: 171 - “Arboras”, “pic Saint-Loup”, “massif de la Gardiole”, “Murviel-lès-Montpellier”, “Aumelas”, “Saint-Georges-d'Orques”, “Cournonterral”, “Saint-Guilhem-le-Désert”; Marquet, 2001: 116 - “Parc naturel régional de la Brenne (Indre)”; Mifsud, 2002: 167 - “Malta”; Sheshurak & Sadovnichia, 2002: 242 - Chernihiv Region; Echevarría Mayo, 2003: 218 - “Ávila”; Valladares et al., 2003: 79 - “Province d'Almeria”;

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- Brustel et al., 2003: 452 - "Villeneuve-les-Maguelonne (Hérault)"; Neculiseanu & Baban, 2005: 202 - "Moldova"; Diego Barquín & Martínez-Porres Cáceres, 2005: 145 - "Cantabria"; Peris-Felipo et al., 2008: 109 - "Parque Natural de La Tinença de Benifassà (Castellón)"; 2010: 362 - "Torrevieja (Alicante)", "Parque Natural de Las Lagunas de La Mata-Torrevieja (Alicante, España)" - (N38°01'56.39" W000°42'47.80", N38°01'59.38" W000°42'44.91", N38°01'49.90" W000°42'00.13", N38°01'19.08" W000°39'51.80", N38°01'00.80" W000°40'24.10", N38°01'50.30" W000°42'40.20", N38°01'01.00" W000°40'22.40", N38°01'50.90" W000°42'34.40"); Mouthiez & Péru, 2008: 110 - "Loiret"; Tiberghien, 2010: 63 - "Arguedas, Navarra; Zaragoza; Pyrénées-Atlantiques"; Bartenev & Terekhova, 2011: 139 - Poltava Region, Kharkov Region, Chernihiv Region; Valladares, 2013: 39 - "Sorbas, Marchalico Viñicas", "Olula de Castro, Sierra de los Filabres", "Agua Amarga", "Nijar"; Cartier & Cartier, 2016: 232 - "Vienne: Quinçay, Vouillé"; Touroult & al., 2019: 105 - France & Corse; Bacal et al., 2020: 59 - Moldova: "Ivanca".
- Agapanthia insularis* Gautier des Cottes, 1870: 263 - "Corse aux environs d'Ajaccio, du côté de l'embouchure de la Gavone; Sicile, environs de Palerme"; Bellier, 1869: 14 - "île de Corse, aux environs d'Ajaccio, embouchure de la Gravone. Sicile, environs de Palerme"; Gemminger & Harold, 1873: 3176 - "Ajaccio"
- Agapanthia reyi* Mulsant & Godart, 1870: 27 - "Patrie: l'Espagne"; Argod, 1891a: 82; 1891b: xxxviii; Pic, 1891a: 38; 1891b: 82; Fauvel, 1895: 116; Winkler, 1929: 1213 - "Gallia meridionalis"; Plavilstshikov, 1930: 18 - "Spanien"; Breuning, 1961: 183 - "Espagne".
- Agapanthia cynarae* var. *delagrangei* Pic, 1894: 75 - "Akbès".
- Agapanthia* (s. str.) *reyi*, Pic, 1910: 95 - "Espagne"; Aurivillius, 1923: 464 - "Spanien".
- Agapanthia* (*Agapanthiella*) *asphodeli*, Özdikmen, 2006: 87 - Turkey: "Ankara: Kızılcahamam, Işık Mountain, Keçikaya hill, 1615 m", "Ankara: Kızılcahamam, Işık Mountain", "Ankara: Kızılcahamam, Soğuksu National Park, 1250 m", "Ankara: Kızılcahamam, Aköz village, 1150 m".
- Agapanthia* (s. str.) *asphodeli*, Pic, 1910: 96 - "Medit."; Plavilstshikov, 1916: 110 - Poltava; Aurivillius, 1923: 459 "Mittelmeer-Gebiet, Böhmen, Siebenbürgen"; Mikšić & Korpič, 1985: 100 - "Pronaden je r Dalmaciji, Hercegovini i Makedoniji"; Önalp, 1989: 199 - France, Spain, Turkey (Çanakkale, Izmir, Bilecik, Ankara, Antalya, Adana, Hatay); Özdikmen & Hasbenly A., 2004: 41 - Turkey: "Isparta: Isparta-Burdur road, exit of Isparta, 1025 m", "Antalya: near Manavgat waterfall, 25 m", "Antalya: Kemer, Olimpos mountain, 561 m", "Isparta: Yalvaç, Sultan mountains, 1596 m", "Isparta: Yalvaç, Sultan mountains, 1674 m", "Yozgat: Çiğdemli, Gökiniş village, 1233 m"; Bartenev, 2004: 41 (= *spencii* Gyllenhal, 1813; = *insularis* Gautier, 1870), part. - Southern Europe, Western Europe, southern European Russia, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Middle East, Turkey, Syria, North Africa Region, Ukraine, Kirovograd Region; 2009: 386 -Ukraine.
- Agapanthia asphodeli* v. *mimica* Pic, 1927: 1 - "Pyr.-Or.".

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Agapanthia (Epoptes) asphodeli, Sama & Rapuzzi, 2011: 142 - Italy: Basilicata, Campania, Lazio, Piemonte, Puglia, Sardegna, Sicilia, Toscana; Steiner & Schmid, 2013: 3; Özdikmen & Tezcan, 2020: 470 - Turkey: İzmir province; Zamoroka, 2022: 64 - "Ukraine"; Trócoli et al., 2023: 245 - Spain: Moianès (Barcelona, Catalogne); Danilevsky, 2023: 592, part.
Agapanthia asphodeli asphodeli, Sláma, 2019: 209 - France: "F 06 St. Rafael, F 86 Riboux, F 66 Banyuls"; "Süd. Spanien, Andalusien".

Type locality. France, Bordeaux environs.

Description. Light parts of antennal joints from reddish to brown, but usually rather pale; black parts of antennal joints can be longer or shorter, from about half of each joint to 1/8 inside each population; elytra without metallic luster; elytral pubescence relatively dense; humeral grey line always absent; body length in males: 15.8-17.2 mm; body length in females: 16.0-23.0 mm.

Material. 1 male, Italy, Roma, Castlfusane De Maggi 11.4.1949 - ML; 1 female, Portugal, Porto - MD; 1 male, Madrid, J. Ardois - ZMM; 1 male, Grecia, 16.5.1973, Schimmel - MD; 1 female, "Rhodes / (Turquie d'Asie) / L. Bleuse" - ZMM; 2 males, 4 females, Turkey, Mersin, Içel, 6.4.1935, ...? - MD; 1 female, Turkey, Karalailyas, 9.4.1935 - MD;; 2 males, 1 female, Turkey, Bandirma env., near Erdek, 40.4196°N 27.8272°E, 80-130 m 21-30.4.2011 S. Murzin - ML, SM; 1 male, Syria, Jebel el Ansariye (northern part), 5.1982, J. Kratochvil - MD; 1 female, Syria, Idlip env., 5.1982, J. Kratochvil - MD; 1 male, "Akbes / Syrien / Em. Reitter" - MD; 1 male, 8 females, "Akbes / Syrien / Em. Reitter" - ZMM; 1 male, Caucasus, Teberda, 3.6.1924 - ZMM.

Holotype of *Agapanthia reyi* Mulsant & Godart, 1870 (Figs 2-3), male with six labels: 1) [red] "HOLOTYPE", 2) "36", 3) "Espagne", 4) "Collect. / Godart", 5) "MUSEUM PARIS / Coll. Godart / Coll A. ARGOD. 1931", 6) "*Reyi* / Muls. & Godart" / Opusc. ent. 14 cahier / p. 27." - MNHN.

Distribution. All species area (with the exception of North Africa, Crete, Cyprus, Lampedusa Island, Peloponnesus and Kastamonu province of Turkey) from West Europe to North Caucasus, including Portugal, Spain, France, Italy, Malta, Croatia, Bosnia et Herzegovina, Macedonia, Albania, Greece, Bulgaria, Romania, Moldova, Ukraine, North Caucasus (Teberda), about whole west half of Anatolia and Syria.

Fig. 1. *Agapanthia (Epoptes) asphodeli asphodeli* (Latreille, 1804): male, Caucasus, Teberda, 3.6.1924.

Figs 2-3. *Agapanthia (Epopetes) asphodeli asphodeli* (Latreille, 1804): 2 - Holotype of *Agapanthia reyi* Mulsant & Godart, 1870, male with six labels: 1) [red] “HOLOTYPE”, 2) “36”, 3) “Espagne”, 4) “Collect. / Godart”, 5) “MUSEUM PARIS / Coll. Godart / Coll A. ARGOD. 1931”, 6) “*Reyi* / Muls. & Godart” / Opusc. ent. 14 cahier / p. 27.”; 3 - labels of *Agapanthia reyi* Mulsant & Godart, 1870.

Agapanthia (Epoetes) asphodeli lopadusae
Rapuzzi & Sparacio, 2017, stat. n.

Agapanthia asphodeli, Pisciotta et.al., 2008: 408 - "Lampedusa, loc. Isola dei Conigli".

Agapanthia (Epoetes) lopadusae Rapuzzi & Sparacio, 2017: 958 - "Italy, Sicilian Channel, Lampedusa Island"; Danilevsky, 2020: 303 - Italy.

Type locality. Italy, Sicilian Channel, Lampedusa Island.

Description. The taxon belongs to *A. asphodeli* because of very elongated third joint of anterior tarsi, reddish 3rd-12th antennal joints, absence of the setae tufts on 3rd antennal joints and regular elytral pubescence.

It can be distinguished from other subspecies by darker antennae which are usually brownish basally from the third segments to the apices. The closest known taxon to *A. a. lopadusae* is *A. a. zappii* from North Africa, but it has distinct grey humeral stripes. Body length: 15.2-19.0 mm.

Distribution. The taxon is known from Lampedusa Island.

Agapanthia (Epoetes) asphodeli renatae
Steiner & Schmid, 2013, stat. n.

Saperda spencii, Brullé, 1832: 261 - "Morée".

Agapanthia asphodeli, Berger, 2005: 93 - "Grèce: Péloponnèse: Dhafnïotisa (Ilia)".

Agapanthia (Epoetes) renatae Steiner & Schmid, 2013: 1, 3 - "Griechenland, Peloponnes, Nomos Arkadias, zwischen Karitena und Kastro, N37°29'10" O22°00'30", 450-550 m Seehöhe"; Danilevsky, 2020: 303 - Greece.

Agapanthia renatae, Rapuzzi & Sparacio, 2017: 957 - "Peloponnese (Greece)"

Agapanthia asphodeli balcanica Sláma, 2019: 208, **syn. n.** - "Graecia, Attiki, Villia", "Graecia, Gerania; Greece, Meteora, 2 km. NE of Kalampaka - Kastraku", "Graecia, prov. Pelloponese, Tripotama env. (Achaia), 40 km SE of Kalavryta, 37°52N, 21°53E, 675 m", "Grece, Pelopones, Arkaia prov., Paradela env.", "Kaesariani Attika".

Agapanthia (Epoetes) asphodeli balcanica, Danilevsky, 2020: 301 - Greece.

Type locality. Greece, Peloponnese, Arcadia, between Karitena and Kastro.

Description. Elytra shining, look glabrous; black apical parts of antennomeres are wider than in the nominative subspecies (France); pronotum is wider (width-to-length ratio is 1.29-1.42); yellow lateral erect pubescence of pronotum is denser and longer; body usually wider and shorter. Body length: 12.0-20.0 mm.

Distribution. Greece, Peloponnese. Attica.

Remarks. *Agapanthia (Eoptes) renatae* Steiner & Schmid, 2013 and *A. (E.) asphodeli balcanica* Sláma, 2019 were both described from one area (Peloponnese), so, it must be regarded as one taxon: *A. renatae* Steiner & Schmid, 2013 = *A. asphodeli balcanica* Sláma, 2019.

***Agapanthia (Eoptes) asphodeli cretica* Bernhauer, 1978, stat. n.**

Agapanthia cretica Bernhauer, 1978: 70 - "Kreta, Ida-Gebirge b. Anogia", "Kreta, Chora Sfakion"; Rapuzzi & Sparacio, 2017: 957 - "Kriti (Greece)".

Agapanthia probsti Holzschuh, 1984: 370, **syn. n.** - "Graecia, Kreta, Nomos Chanion, Omalos, 1000 m", "Kreta, Lefka Ori, 3.7 km vor Omalos, 900 m", "Kreta, SW Lefka Ori, Ag. Irini, 900 m".

Agapanthia (Agapanthiella) cretica, Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2004: 127.

Agapanthia (Agapanthiella) probsti, Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2004: 127.

Agapanthia (Eoptes) cretica, Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 215 - Greece (Kriti); Steiner & Schmid, 2013: 2, 3; Danilevsky, 2020: 301 - Crete.

Agapanthia (Eoptes) probsti, Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 216 - Greece (Kriti); Steiner & Schmid, 2013: 2; Danilevsky, 2020: 303 - Crete.

Type locality. Crete, Mount Ida, Anogia.

Description. The taxon is distinctly different from closely related other subspecies of the group by dark elytra and its strong luster; eyes small; antennae relatively short, only about one third longer than body in males, or about just a little longer; black space of each antennal joint is relatively small, occupies a top apex of 3rd joint, about apical 1/3 of 3rd joint, and about halves of other joints; antennal tufts absent, just several single setae present near top of each joint; prothorax transverse, enlarged posteriorly, lateral and dorsal pronotal stripes very dense and orange, as well as marginal elytral stripes; elytra nearly glabrous, with indistinct setae spots, without humeral elytral stripes; in males about 3 times longer than wide, or about 2.6 times longer than wide in females; body length: 10.5-16.5 mm.

Material. "*Ag. probsti*": 1 male, 1 female, Creta, Theviso, 6.1985, P. Schurmann - MD; "*Ag. cretica*": 3 males, 1 female, Creta, Chora Sfakion, 4.1982 - MD; 3 males, 7 females, Creta, Chora Sfakion, 22.3.1991 M.Sláma - MD; 1 male, Creta, Biro, Canea, 12.3.1906 - MD.

Remarks. *Agapanthia cretica* Bernhauer, 1978 was described from Crete. *A. probsti* Holzschuh, 1984 was in fact undistinguished from *A. cretica* and also described from Crete - from about same type

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locality - so, *Agapanthia cretica* Bernhauer, 1978 (13.0-16.0 mm) =
A. probsti Holzschuh, 1984 (10.5-13.8 mm).

***Agapanthia (Epoptes) asphodeli kastamonica* ssp. n.**

Figs 4-6

Type locality. Turkey, Kastamonu province, Yaralığöz Dağı.

Description. The taxon differs from European populations by extremely big eyes, lower eye lobe about 3 times longer than genae; antennae relatively short, about one fourth longer than body in males, or by about 5 apical joints surpassing elytral apex; in females antennae surpassing elytral apex by 2 joints only; black space of each antennal joint is relatively small, occupies a top of 3rd joint, about apical 1/3 of 4th joint, and a little less than a half of other joints; antennal tufts absent, just several single setae present near joint apices; prothorax transverse, enlarged posteriorly; pronotal stripes light yellow; dorsal pronotal and lateral elytral stripes poorly developed; elytra very dark with rather dense punctation; nearly glabrous, with indistinct setae spots, without humeral elytral stripe; in males about 2.6 times longer than wide, or about 2.3 times longer than wide in females; body length: 17.0-18.0 mm.

Material. Holotype, male, Turkey, Kastamonu, Yaraligoz, 7.7.1997, N. Auvray - ML; 1 paratype, female with same label - ML.

Distribution. Turkey, Kastamonu province, Yaralığöz Dağı [41°45'N, 34°10'E].

Etymology. The new taxon is named after its locality.

Figs 4-5. *Agapanthia (Epopetes) asphodeli kastamonica* ssp. n.:
4 - Holotype, male, Turkey, Kastamonu, Yaraligoz, 7.7.1997,
N. Auvray; 5 - paratype, female with same label.

Figs 6-7. Heads, lateral views, males: 6 - *Agapanthia (Epoetes) asphodeli kastamonica* **ssp. n.**, holotype; 7 - *A. (E.) a. asphodeli* (Latreille, 1804), Greece, 16.5.1973, Schimmel leg.

***Agapanthia (Epoetes) asphodeli nicosiensis* Pic, 1927, stat. rest.**

Agapanthia dahli nicosiensis Pic, 1927: 1 - "Chypre".

Agapanthia dahli m. *nicosiensis*, Breuning, 1961: 185.

Agapanthia nicosiensis, Rapuzzi & Sparacio, 2017: 957 - "Cyprus".

Agapanthia (Agapanthiella) nicosiensis, Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2004: 127.

Agapanthia (Epoetes) nicosiensis, Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 216 - Cyprus; Ambrus, Grosser & Hrbek, 2014: 188 "Cyprus, 26 km SW Larnaka, 3 km N Skarinou, Dhypotamos Dam env.", "Cyprus, Pafos, Agia Varvara", "Cyprus, Akamas peninsula, 27 km N Paphos, 3 km W Neo Chorio, Camping site "Smigies" env.", "Cyprus, Larnaca distr., Lageia env., 34°50'6.00"N 33°15'33.48"E"; Danilevsky, 2020: 303 - Cyprus.

Type locality. Cyprus.

Description. Eyes small; elytra with dense, spotted yellow pubescence and distinct grey humeral stripes; pale basal parts of 3rd-12th antennal joints light-red; setae tufts of 3rd antennal joints well developed; elytra in males about 2.8 times longer than wide; body length: 16.0-18.0 mm.

Distribution. Cyprus.

Material. 1 male, Cyprus, Nicosia - MD.

***Agapanthia (Epopetes) asphodeli zappii* Sama, 1987, stat. n.**

Agapanthia cynarae, Lucas, 1847: 499 -pl. 42, figs 6, 6a, environs du cercle de Lacalle, lieux qui avoisinent les lacs Tonga et Houbeira. ; environs d'Arzew.

Agapanthia asphodeli, Villiers, 1946: 118 - "Méditerranéenne", "Maroc: Mogador, Tanger, Mèknes, Méhilla, Fès, Sefrou, Forêts de la Mamora et des Zaers, Oujda, Talmest (2200 m), Tizi n'Tislet, Dj. Amar", Algérie: Arzew, Oran, Saint-Charles, Téniet el Haad, Tunisie, Forêts de Yakouren, Alger, Constantine, La Calle, Lacs Tonga et Houbeira", "Tunisie: El Feidja, Le Kef, Souk el Arba"; Heyrovský, 1937: 7 - "Libaah, Djezin, Chtaura, Saïda".

Agapanthia zappii Sama, 1987: 62 - "Algérie (Batna): col de Telmet (Aurès)", "Maroc, Juadi Mellah", Maroc, dint. Zaouia Temga", "Maroc, Casablanca", "Maroc, Salé", "Maroc, Agadir", "tra Taddert et Tizi-n'Ticka, 1650-2200 m", "Libia (Tripolitania), Homs"; Chavanon, 1999: 171 - "Maroc Oriental: entre Oujda et Guenfouda"; Rapuzzi & Sparacio, 2017: 957 - "in North Africa from Lybia to Morocco"; Sama, Ringenbach & Rejzek, 2005: 448 - Libya.

Agapanthia (Agapanthiella) zappii, Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2004: 127.

Agapanthia (Epopetes) zappii, Chavanon et al., 2014: 296 "Aklim, 34°52'N - 02°31'W, 72 m", "sud du col de Jerada, 34°17'N - 02°04'W, 1044 m", "Taourirt, route d'Oujda, au pont sur l'oued Sifsif, 34°29'N - 02°53'W, 355 m", "Saka, route de Nador, km 15, 34°41'N - 03°19'W, 580 m"; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 216 - Algeria, Lybia, Morocco, Tunisia; Chavanon, 2018: 106 - Morocco, Oriental Region, Guercif Provinces: "alentours du barrage Elhassi Labyad (au sud du col de Jerada) et toute la région située au nord d'une ligne Guercif-Touissit"; Danilevsky, 2020: 303 - Algeria, Lybia, Morocco, Tunisia; Kasatkin, 2020: 246; Trócoli, 2020: 29 - "Maroc: entre Oujda et Guenfouda"; Trócoli, 2023: 210 - Morocco, "Ifrane, Dayet Ahoua, 1467 m".

Agapanthia (Epopetes) asphodeli, Cocquemot et al., 2016: 99 - Liban; Trócoli, 2020: 29 - "Le Nord, Centre et Ouest du Maroc, entre Oujda, Tanger, Casablanca et l'Atlas central, parfois plus au sud, dans la région côtière de Essaouira, Agadir"; Trócoli, 2023: 210 - Morocco, "Bouznika", "Khemiset", "Imilchil".

Type locality. Algeria (Batna): Telmet canyon (Aures Mountains), 1700 m.

Description. According to Trócoli (2020), *A. zappii* Sama, 1987 is very close to *A. asphodeli*: "Ce sont deux espèces très proches, et *zappii* n'est peut-être qu'une variété d'*asphodeli*". So, it must be accepted as a southern subspecies *A. asphodeli zappii* Sama, 1987,

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stat. n. *A. a. asphodeli* is also known from Morocco, but observed usually in the north part of the country. Still the areas of both taxa shown by Trócoli (2020) in his areal maps coincided totally.

A. asphodeli zappii differs from the nominative subspecies by elytral pubescence short, lighter, grey-yellow, with grey contrast humeral band; body length: 12.0-16.0 mm.

Distribution. North Africa (Morocco, Lybia, Algeria, Tunisia).

Material. 1 male, Morocco, Region Souss-Massa-Daraa, Prefecture Agadir-Ida ou Tanane, Commune Ida ou Tanane, 12 km E Aourir, 23.1.2002, Øistein Berg - MD; 1 male, paratype, Maroc., umg. Agadir, 12.85 Dr. Schurmann - MD; 1 female, paratype, Algeria, Batna, Col de Telmet, 1700 m, 11.6.1980, G. Sama & G. Magnani - MD.

Agapanthia (Epopetes) asphodeli fadli Sama & Rapuzzi, 2006, stat. n.

Agapanthia lateralis, Alfieri, 1916: 70 - "Egypte"; Petroff, 1919: 64 - "environs d'Alexandrie".

Agapanthia fadli Sama & Rapuzzi, 2006: 186 - "14 km east of Burg al 'Arab (west of Alexandria), 30°58'N 29°40'E", "Egypt: "Mariut / Mars / Soc. Roy. Entom. Egypte / Faune d'Egypte", "Hammam / (Dakahlich) / Egitto"; "Marzo / Faune d'Egypte", "Maryout: Kinghi; Hammam, Abu Mina, Ikinghi Maryut, Damietta; El Borg; Burg el-Arab"; Rapuzzi & Sparacio, 2017: 957 - "North Egypt".

Agapanthia (Epopetes) fadli, Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 215 - Egypt; Danilevsky, 2020: 303 - Egypt.

Type locality. Egypt, 14 km east of Burg al 'Arab (west of Alexandria), 30°58'N 29°40'E.

Description. Body dark with strong bronze luster; lower eyes lobes short, about as long as genae; pronotum densely rugose; prothorax transverse, enlarged posteriorly; pronotal stripes light yellow; dorsal pronotal and lateral elytral stripes poorly developed; antennae long, about one half longer than body in males, or about 5 apical joints longer than body; 3rd antennal segment with a small setae tuft; black space of each antennal joint is relatively small, occupies a top apex of 3rd joint, about apical 1/3 of 3rd joint, and about halves of other joints; elytra densely setose, but setae spots indistinct, without humeral elytral stripe; elytra in males about 2.6 times longer than wide; body length: 11.0-21.0 mm.

Distribution. The taxon is known from Egypt only.

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